

What is the potential impact of the transition from traditional transport to new mobility (automated minibuses) in European cities?

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Abstract

As a prime contender to revolutionise the global auto industry, automated vehicles deployment in cities and within the transport ecosystem requires further investigation. This has also become a prime concern because of the current Covid-19 situation. The introduction of automated minibuses could cause major modal shifts towards or away from public transport. Thus, it is crucial to predict potential deployments and determine their implications to avoid repeating an individual-centric mobility model. This paper suggests possible future scenarios of automated minibuses deployment and calculates the environmental impact through externalities caused by these modal shifts (from traditional transport to automated minibuses).

Based on scenario planning and externalities calculations, a methodology is presented and applied to a case study of Geneva using data from a mobility census of Geneva in 2015 and insights from a European project, AVENUE. First, the analysis presents marginal external costs for the automated minibuses. Then, it describes 3 scenarios that highlight the integration of the automated minibuses in public transport and their effects on modal shares. The assessment shows that replacing all cars with automated minibuses produces the best savings of externalities. Replacing all buses with automated minibuses leads to higher externalities. The integration of the automated minibuses as part of mobility-as-a-service MaaS is the most feasible and scalable. The study emphasises the role of targeted policies to optimise the benefits of automated minibuses.

1. Introduction

Smart mobility is poised to cause a socio-economic transition of transportation systems in cities (Garau, Masala, & Pinna, 2016; Lyons, 2018). The deployment of Automated Vehicles (AV) could be part of this transition, depending on the potential deployment strategies. Several deployment strategies are possible. On the one hand, AV could be used to further enforce the current status quo of the domination of individual motorised vehicles. On the other, it could present a disruptive and beneficial change to the mobility paradigm in the form of shared AV, such as Automated minibuses (AM) integrated into public transport (PT) (Stocker & Shaheen, 2017).

The current COVID-19 pandemic increased the importance of improving public transport systems, as the measures taken by governments worldwide to restrict the pandemic have caused acute disruptions in public transport (The world bank, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic also highlights the vulnerabilities of the public transport ecosystem, as accessible, safe, and reliable services have become more important (Jenelius & Cebecauer, 2020; Liu, Miller, & Scheff, 2020).

Recent studies find that the deployment of shared AV, offering an on-demand, door-to-door service, could reduce car-ownership, impact travel behaviour, enhance public transport services, and eventually lead to smart and livable cities (Nogués, González-González, & Cordera, 2020). Thus, AM could provide a solution to the unsustainability of the transport sector and increase public transport competitiveness, depending on the applied deployment strategies.

The deployment of AV and consequent changes in mobility will impact modal shares, congestion, air and noise pollution, climate change, and accidents (Fagnant & Kockelman, 2015). However, the actual impacts of the different deployment strategies of AV are currently unknown. Therefore, this study aims to

determine suitable models for future AV deployment in urban areas. We are specifically interested in models that can reduce car dependency through targeted transportation demand management (TDM) measures and policies for mobility externalities internalisation. Likewise, it is from our interest models aligned with the Sustainable Urban Mobility Planning (SUMP) approach, which builds on existing planning practices in an attempt to reduce private car dependency and transport externalities (Diez, Lopez-Lambas, Gonzalo, Rojo, & Garcia-Martinez, 2018; May, 2015). Moreover, we rely on observations from AVENUE, a H2020 project, that focuses on on-demand, door-to-door, automated minibuses. The observations are part of a dedicated workpackage of environmental, social, and economic impact assessment. The workpackage includes the externalities calculation aligned with life cycle assessment and representative surveys to design a roadmap of AM deployment in cities. In this study, on a first basis, we focus on the automated minibuses without the on-demand service, we also rely on national survey. But we will use AVENUE survey results and explain better the effects of on-demand services in the future.

In recent years, there has been considerable interest in using scenario planning to predict the future of AV (Bagloee, Tavana, Asadi, & Oliver, 2016; González-González, Nogués, & Stead, 2020; ITF, 2015, 2017; Milakis, Snelder, van Arem, van Wee, & Homem De Almeida Correia, Gonçalo, 2017; Mourad, Puchinger, & Chu, 2019; Nogués et al., 2020; Ross & Guhathakurta, 2017; Townsend, 2014; Vleugel & Bal, 2017). For instance, Milakis et al. (2017) presented four scenarios based on technology advancement and policies to estimate different AVs' penetration rates and the effects of the urban environment on the deployment. They also predict that shared AV could diminish the role of traditional public transport by luring passengers with flexible options. The simulation in Lisbon conducted by the International Transportation Forum (ITF) focuses on the availability of high-capacity public transport and its effect on the deployment of shared AV but with a fixed modal shift of 50% (ITF, 2015). Moreover, we cite González-González et al. (2020). They study the effect of AV on European cities and parking space using scenarios. Similarly to Milakis et al. (2017) see the shared AV as a potential competitor of public transport and active modes. They report a potential reduction of 16% in PT and 26% in active modes. We further build on this previous work, and we focus on the AM as a solution for public transport. Our research addresses the effect on PT and considers scenarios where AM does not lead to a modal shift from public transport. It also focuses more on the minibuses instead of the ride-sharing and car-sharing schemes for AV.

Furthermore, mobility external costs help us to measure the impact of modal shift towards the AV. Recently, several studies analysed external costs of different transportation modes (Fournier et al., 2020; Girardi, Brambilla, & Mela, 2020; Jochem, Doll, & Fichtner, 2016; Musso & Rothengatter, 2013; Ogden, Williams, & Larson, 2004; van Essen et al., 2019). These studies provide the marginal and total external costs for traditional road transport (Musso & Rothengatter, 2013; van Essen et al., 2019), electric cars (Girardi et al., 2020; Jochem et al., 2016; Ogden et al., 2004), and robotaxis (Fournier et al., 2020). However, none of these studies focuses on estimating the marginal external costs of automated electric minibuses. This paper aims to contribute to this gap of knowledge by addressing the potential impacts of the deployment of AM. It, therefore, investigates the following research question: what is the potential impact of the transition from traditional transport to new mobility, including AM, in European cities?

In order to address this question, this study combines the calculation of externalities with scenario planning and applies it to the case study of Geneva. The city of Geneva deploys an on-demand AM service. This initiative is part of AVENUE, an EU-funded project which aims at enhancing public transport by offering innovative urban mobility services, as automated, on-demand and door-to-door trips. In this study, we

assess potential scenarios of mobility transition with the AM in Geneva. The assessment provides valuable findings of the potential savings and losses in externalities according to the modal shift triggered by the AM (section 3). Further, the scenarios and externalities savings from introducing automated minibuses provide insights for recommendations and strategies to internalisation policies, TDM measures, and promote sustainable mobility.

To answer the research question, the paper starts with a methodology section, in which we present the research framework and detail the different methods. Second, we present the results of the Geneva case study. Finally, we provide a discussion of our findings and conclude with a conclusion section.

2. Methodology

To assess the external costs of mobility and the possible gains or losses in externalities caused by introducing AM in the urban mobility system, our methodological approach combines the calculation of externalities with scenario planning (see figure 1). The externalities calculation follows the methodology presented in CE Delft (van Essen et al., 2019). A detailed description is presented in section 2.1. The scenario planning is conducted based on the Intuitive Logic Approach (Lloyd & Schweizer, 2014). A detailed description of this approach is presented in section 2.2.

Based on the calculation of externalities and the scenarios, we can assess the avoidance costs by saved externalities when replacing traditional modes of transport by the AM. To do so, we apply a selection of scenarios to the case study of Geneva. Details of the selection of Geneva as a case study are presented in section 2.4. Five steps are conducted to calculate the avoidance costs:

1. An important first step is to calculate the reference scenario; the current modal split and the average distances per mode of transport are used to derive the transport performance in person-kilometre pkm¹. This lays out the reference point to compare with the scenarios and provides the avoidance costs.
2. In a second step, we calculated for each scenario the modal share of the AM based on a modal shift from other modes of transport. These different modal splits lead to different impacts and externalities.
3. Third, the Marginal costs (MC) (€-cent/pkm) for road transport and AM is fixed for Geneva and the scenarios.
4. Fourth, we can predict the total externalities (million euros) in Geneva for the scenarios by combining the transport performance in pkm from the different modal shares with the MC.
5. Finally, the study delivers avoidance costs by comparing the reference point with each scenario. See Figure 1.

¹ Person kilometer represents the total distances covered by persons within a year, it reflects transport performance and depends on vehicle occupancy. FSO (2019)

Figure 1: Methodology of the study

2.1. Externalities methodology

External costs are defined as the indirect and uncompensated impact of one group's social and economic activities on a third party (Pigou, 1920; Pigou, 2017; van Essen et al., 2019). More specifically, transport externalities are the costs that are not born by road users but are caused by them, such as air pollution and noise. According to the CE Delft report by van Essen et al. (2019): *“External costs of transport refer to the difference between social costs (i.e. all costs to society due to the provision and use of transport infrastructure) and private costs of transport (i.e. the costs directly borne by the transport user).”* Externalities present a tool to compare the environmental sustainability of different modes of transportations (Jochem et al., 2016). This comparison could further be used to implement urban policies. Implementing internalisation policies (command and control, incentive-based policies, pull policies) helps mitigate these costs. The endgame is to provide policymakers with strong guidelines on how to proceed for long-end policy planning to ensure smart and sustainable mobility integration in cities (Janasz, 2018; Paccagnan et al., 2008). The introduction of AM presents an alternative to prevent the environmental deterioration of conventional transportation. This could be captured through the externalities savings and costs. They present imputed costs of limiting the environmental damage by reducing the use of individual transport (OECD, 2001; United Nations, 1997).

The assessment is focused on replacing different transport modes with AM. The means of transportation are standard buses, internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEV), active mobility: walking and biking. The external costs are estimated using The Handbook on External Costs of Transport by CE Delft for the European Commission (van Essen et al., 2019). It relies on national short-run marginal costs (MC) (€-cent/pkm), which are defined as the additional external cost caused by an additional transport activity on

a constant infrastructure capacity and do not account for future expansions. The association between these costs and the transport performance (in pkm) provides the total external costs (million euros). The assessment of the environmental externalities follows the life cycle assessment (LCA). The LCA aims at analysing the composition of materials and their environmental damage potential. The LCA comprises the emissions caused by well-to-wheel processes (Jochem et al., 2016). A well-to-wheel analysis focuses on the Full fuel-cycle emissions: the use of the vehicle and the upstream operations (Ogden et al., 2004). The well-to-wheel (WTW) is composed of 2 parts: well-to-tank (WTT) and tank-to-wheel (TTW). TTW includes the use of energy and the associated emission during driving, while WTT focuses on the emission of energy production (JCR, 2016; Woo, Choi, & Ahn, 2017).

We consider the externalities of air pollution, climate change, noise, accidents, and congestion. The impacts categories that are included in this study are:

- Air pollution:
 - health effects (medical costs, loss of work productivity due to sickness), crop losses, building damage (damage to surfaces, facades, and materials), and biodiversity ((soil and water acidification, eutrophication of ecosystems).
 - The pollutants are PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO_x, SO₂, and NMVOC using a damage cost approach
- Climate change:
 - the effects related to global warming - sea level rise, biodiversity loss, water management difficulties, extreme weather conditions, and crop failures.
 - The emissions are of CO₂, N₂O, and CH₄ using the avoidance cost approach
- Noise exposure:
 - annoyance and health effects caused by road traffic noise.
 - The noise impact is determined using a damage cost approached on 5dB thresholds from noise maps from EEA (2014). The willingness-to-pay to avoid the nuisance of noise reflects the annoyance, and the value-of-statistical-life reflects the health concerns.
- Accidents:
 - material damage, production losses, and administrative, medical, and human costs
 - The damage cost approach estimates the social costs of traffic accidents that are not covered by risk-oriented insurance. Human costs are a way to represent the pain and suffering caused by traffic accidents
- Congestion:
 - external costs of congestion result from not meeting passengers' mobility demand due to the temporary scarcity of infrastructure. In other words, this cost occurs when an additional vehicle enters the traffic flow; it reduces the speed and increases the travel time.
 - It accounts for delays, unreliable travel times, extra operation costs, and loss in economic activity

The different estimations for the AM are further explained within the study case (section 3.2) since they are context-based. They are determined before the total externalities. The estimations for the MC for ICEV and buses and the methodology used to estimate the different values are adapted from van Essen et al. (2019). A detailed overview of the estimations is presented in (Viere, Nemoto, Jaroudi, & Korbee, 2021)

2.2. Scenario planning

Scenario planning and analysis help provide forecasts of the future. It relies on qualitative and quantitative data to recognise what agents could lead to drastic change (González-González et al., 2020; Huss & Honton, 1987).

It is also used to improve decision-making and strategy development (Derbyshire & Wright, 2017; Wright, Bradfield, & Cairns, 2013).

According to Schoemaker (1995), scenario planning is “A disciplined method for imaging possible futures in which organisational decisions may be played out. Scenarios are subjective”. They depend on qualitative analysis, storytelling, simulations, and characteristics called driving forces (Lindgren & Bandhold, 2009). The method used for scenario planning in this paper builds on the Intuitive Logics Approach (ILA) to predict future deployment strategies for the AM and estimate the potential modal shifts as well as the externalities (Lloyd & Schweizer, 2014; Milakis et al., 2017). The ILA was developed for business management with companies such as SRI International and Shell. It analyses external factors external (economic, political, environmental, technological, and social) that could affect business decisions within private companies. These factors are either quantitative and predictable, such as demographics, while others are qualitative and less predictable, such as user acceptance and policies (Huss & Honton, 1987; Lindgren & Bandhold, 2009). The ILA strength lies in its flexibility. However, it falls short in quantitative analysis, hence why this study relies on the externalities to render the model more robust.

This method is usually devised of 8 steps. However, we can sum it in 3 steps for our analysis as is presented in Figure 2

The driving forces are critical to defining the deployment efforts, while key factors present general trends of AM introduction. We use similar reasoning to Townsend (2014) to identify the driving forces in this study. The author frames his scenarios by considering the transportation system in general and the separate components of technology and services. Hence, the scenarios presented are distinguished by the following driving forces are:

- Technology advancement;
- urban policy (political agenda for mobility and sustainability);
- transportation offer (trends of use and modes available);
- the users (most likely to use the AM in the scenario).

These driving forces help in embedding the AM in societal and political contexts. As for the key factors, they were determined through a deliberative process within the AVENUE team. Indeed, the trial sites, the interdisciplinary nature of the project, as well as the work of (Beukers, 2019; Korbee, Naderer, Dubielzig, Mathe, & Helfer, 2021; Viere et al., 2021)) were used to select the following key factors:

- whether the AM are replacing one mode of transport or multiple modes;
- whether AM supports or competes with public transport (replace buses modal share or not) see Figure 2

Figure 2: 3 steps for the intuitive logic approach

The Intuitive logic matrix (Figure 3) is a tool that helps group the scenarios and distinguish between them thanks to the polarity of the key factors; in this case, the replacement of one or more mode of transport by the AM and their relation with public transport.

Figure 3: Intuitive logic matrix; The general method and the application to AVENUE

2.3. Case study choice: the AVENUE project and city of Geneva

Understanding the implications of introducing new technology into the mobility system is a challenging feat. Relying on a field-based example, it becomes easier to cope with the technology's potential effects and eventually answer the research question. Thus, we consider the AVENUE project and Geneva city as our case study to ground the research.

The AVENUE project is an H2020 funded project with four years duration (2018 to 2022). AVENUE has deployed AM in the public transport of four European cities: Geneva, Lyon, Luxembourg and Copenhagen. The project has as main objective to enhance public transport by offering innovative urban mobility services, as automated, on-demand and door-to-door trips (Beukers, 2019). This service could improve passengers' flexibility, convenience and environmental friendliness mobility. Therefore, it is in the scope of the project's social, environmental and economic impact assessments to investigate the integration of AM into the mobility system. Hence, the externalities study is framed on the AVENUE impact assessments. As a demonstrator city within the AVENUE project, the city of Geneva hosts two pilot projects:

- Meyrin pilot has a fixed route of 2,1 km, frequency of every 30 minutes, and the passengers are residents of the area.
- Belle-Idée pilot operates in a hospital area, the service offered is on-demand and door-to-door, the passengers are mainly patients, employees and visitors of the hospital. This pilot is in a test phase.

For this study, we chose the Geneva case study. The insights about the mobility system gained from the AVENUE partners helped develop a good understanding of the particularities of transportation in Geneva (e.g. modal share, mobility behaviour, mobility costs, infrastructure) and the innovative context of the city and pilot sites.

2.4 Boundaries, assumptions and limitations

To assess the total savings or costs, we have to set boundaries and make assumptions. The main scenarios selected for the case study reflect the boundary of our focus on urban areas. This is based on the central goal to study the potential deployment of AM in European cities. This is particularly important when it comes to selecting the MC for the different modes of transport. A second system boundary is a focus on road passenger transportation. This means that we do not integrate rail-based transportation, such as tram, metro and train. However, road passenger transportation does include ICEV, buses, biking, walking, motorcycles, and micro-mobility (i.e. scooters).

To be able to calculate the external costs, and based on previous studies, we assume the following:

- i) The AM deployment could affect motorised mobility, public transport and active mobility (Janasz, 2018). The AM are introduced in mixed traffic (with no prior presence of automated technology on the roads).
- ii) Every additional person-kilometre travelled on the AM is travelled less on the other transportation modes. Therefore, the total transport performance remains identical compared to the reference scenario (Bubeck et al. 2014).
- iii) Active mobility's negative externalities as walking, biking are considered negligible (Keall, Shaw, Chapman, & Howden-Chapman, 2018).
- iv) The study does not account for the increase in transport performance due to population increase and other socio-demographic changes; we are more focused on the effect of unpredictable factors such as the integration within the transportation system and policies. The population growth is predictable and easy to estimate. That is why we chose to simplify the calculations by omitting its effects (Huss & Honton, 1987).
- v) Intermodal trips consist of two or more modes of transport (car/bus/walking/biking+train) (Fraedrich, Beiker, & Lenz, 2015), while monomodal or unimodal trips are considered one mode
- vi) Walking trips accounted as a mode of transport for intermodal trips from 600 m or more (more than 5 minutes) (Gebhardt et al., 2016)
- vii) The average speed of circulation for all vehicles ranges from 25 to 30 km/h
- viii) The shuttles operate on "other urban roads", and we estimate that the average traffic flow² is near capacity.

Furthermore, we acknowledge the limitation of the methodology. First, the ILA is a subjective and speculative method. The complexity of socio-economic changes, the numerous variables at play, and relying on 2 key uncertainties lead to a small sample of the vast pool of potential future (Amer, Daim, & Jetter, 2013; Derbyshire & Wright, 2017). Second, externalities calculations present numerous challenges: cost categories (average and marginal³), different impact evaluations (avoidance, damage cost), different scales (EU, national), emissions valuation (global warming potential, impact pathway approach), and meta-

² Traffic flow= volume of traffic /capacity of a traffic on a link ('near capacity' is v/c between 0.8 and 1, 'congested' between 1 and 1.2, 'over capacity' is above 1.2)

³ Average costs present the average all external costs within a geographical boundary, while marginal costs reflect the impact of an additional vehicle entering the road.

data sets (Dbl noise maps, traffic and emission data). Notably, studies (i.e.(van Essen et al., 2019)) provide a comprehensive best practice approach to deal with these complexities (Jochem et al., 2016)

3. The assessment – the model application – the study case

3.1. Scenario description

The scenarios are designed to gauge the potential economic and environmental effects of this innovation as well as the implications for the transportation system and mobility trends. The deliberative process with AVENUE partners helped pinpoint multiple key factors that might affect the successful and sustainable deployment of the AM. The selection was based on the actual dissemination efforts and the AM role within public transport and within a MaaS platform (Beukers, 2019)

The key factors that were selected can be divided into two groups. The first group (on the X-axis in Figure 4) highlights the integration of the AM in the public transportation system. The first factor is the deployment of AM as a competitor to current public transport. Hence the AM will replace buses (this translates to “PT competitor” in Figure 4). The second key factor is the deployment of AM as a supporter of the public transport system. Hence, they will not replace buses but will strengthen connectivity and access to trains and buses. The second group (on the Y-axis) highlights the type of trip that AM replaces. They could replace one mode of transport (e.g. cars or buses), while the other key factor translates to replacing a combination of modes of transport rather than just one (e.g. cars and buses).

Considering the user acceptability and results from the pilot sites, the scenarios were built to translate the importance of filling public transportation gaps, addressing car dependency, and considering the potential effect on other sustainable transportation modes. Notably, it is a speculative process and relies on prospective predictions from previous literature as well. Thus 6 scenarios were assigned based on the ILA method; they are placed in the ILA matrix in Figure 4. The description of these is in Table 1.

Figure 4: The 6 scenarios of AVENUE in the ILA matrix

Table 1: The description of the AVENUE scenarios

Scenario	modal shifts	Description	references
1 Replace all buses	– Replace standard buses in the city	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>Driving forces:</u> 1-<i>Technological development:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AM platooning, improved sensory capabilities V2X, level 5 automation 2-<i>Urban policy:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high push for technology and smart cities initiatives, use of mobility innovations 3-<i>transport offer:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AM fare is cheap - limited introduction of electric buses - Buses are obsolete, no significant innovation in standard buses to improve their environmental effects, not connected to MaaS services - congestion in city centres deter people from using individual mobility, so bus riders will not use cars instead 4-<i>User:</i> bus riders ▪ <u>Consequences:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mostly replacing monomodal trips by bus - no effect on walking and biking 	(Bimbraw, 2015; Coppola & Morisio, 2016; Iclodean, Cordos, & Varga, 2020; ITF, 2017; Leich & Bischoff, 2019; Zawieska & Pieriegud, 2018)
2 - Serves new areas	Replace the car modal share in areas with no PT with AM in suburban and interurban areas in order to expand the PT network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>Driving forces:</u> 1-<i>Technological development:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - higher speeds, on-demand service, level 5/4 automation 2-<i>Urban policy</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increase access on a regional level, - decrease reliance on individual vehicles, - reduce urban development pressure in urban settlement's by facilitating the commute in and outside of cities 3- <i>transport offer:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PT limited in suburban areas, reliance on cars 4-<i>User:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - private car owners who are monomodal and travel for long distances (more than 5 km), mainly in suburban areas ▪ <u>Consequences:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No effect on walking or biking - Minibuses might travel with less capacity to provide comfort and save time for passengers (comparable to private cars) - interurban areas become more attractive (urban sprawl) 	(Bernhart, Kaiser, Ohashi, Schönberg, & Schilles, 2018; González-González et al., 2020; Hinderer, Stegmüller, Schmidt, Sommer, & Lucke, 2018; ITF, 2017; Murray, Davis, Stimson, & Ferreira, 1998) (Beukers, 2019)
3 targeted operation of AM	- Replace the car share in areas with no PT with AM (scenario 2) and Replace nocturnal buses and empty running buses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <u>Driving forces:</u> 1-<i>Technological development:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - higher speeds, on-demand service, level 5/4 automation 2-<i>Urban policy</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increase access on a regional level, - decrease reliance on individual vehicles, - reduce urban development pressure in urban settlement's by facilitating the commute in and outside of cities - optimise PT, and reduce costs for public transport operators 3- <i>transport offer:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PT limited in suburban areas, reliance on cars 4-<i>User:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - private car owners who are monomodal and travel for long distances (more than 5 km), mainly in suburban areas (remote areas passengers) - night time passengers ▪ <u>Consequences:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No effect on walking or biking - Minibuses might travel with less capacity to provide comfort and save time for passengers (comparable to private cars) - urban sprawl 	(Bernhart et al., 2018; Hinderer et al., 2018; Krueger et al., 2016; McCallum, 2020; Murray et al., 1998) (Beukers, 2019)

4 – AM in MaaS (AM as public transportation feeder in intermodal mobility)

-Replace walking trips more than 600 m in intermodal trips
 -Replace car and biking trips in intermodal trips
 -Replace other less used modes of transport (motorcycles)

- Driving forces:
- 1-*Technological development:*
 - MaaS platform, improved sensory capabilities V2X, level 5 automation
- 2-*Urban policy*
 - Strategy to support public transport and increase connectivity
 - increase accessibility and access,
 - 0-emission strategy in the city
 - focus on Smart city initiatives and MaaS solutions
 - limit access of cars to city centres (fuel and parking measures)
- 3- *transport offer:*
 - emphasis on seamless travel
 - environmental modes of transport are preferable
 - strong public transport
- 4-*User:*
 - Intermodal travellers (last and first mile passengers)
- Consequences:
 - Replace some walking and biking
 - Increase the attractiveness of cities (effects on real-estate pricing)

(Bimbraw, 2015; Gebhardt et al., 2016; Giansoldati, Danielis, & Rotaris, 2020; González-González et al., 2020; Kagerbauer, Hilgert, Schroeder, & Vortisch, 2015; Paydar, Fard, & Khaghani, 2020; Tirachini, 2015; Yap, Correia, & van Arem, 2016; Zawieska & Pieriegud, 2018)

5 - Private AM

- Similar to Uberpool
 -replace some of the bus shares
 replace car use
 Replace walking trips more than 600 m

- Driving forces:
- 1-*Technological development:*
 - digital features designed to provide comfort and attract customers (wifi onboard), Private Maas Platform, on-demand, swarm intelligence
- 2-*Urban policy*
 - minimal transport demand management,
 - no restrictions on individual mobility
 - no strategy on public transport
- 3- *transport offer:*
 - Public transport not efficient and not accessible to all
 - individual mobility is competitive with an improved environmental footprint
 - Private operators in control aim to increase competitiveness and revenue,
- 4-*User:*
 - travellers seeking convenience
- Consequences:
 - Needs more infrastructure development
 - Deteriorating PT due to lack of funding and users
 - replaces walking (based on Value Of Time, it is cheaper to take an AM rather than walk)

(Fournier et al., 2020; Lo & Morseman, 2018; Rayle, Dai, Chan, Cervero, & Shaheen, 2016; Ward, Michalek, Azevedo, Samaras, & Ferreira, 2019)

6. replace all cars

Replace cars in the city

- Driving forces:
- Technological development:*
 - similar to scenario 1
- 2-*Urban policy*
 - similar to scenario 4
 - no long-term plan or anticipation for the effect of eliminating individual motorised mobility
- 3- *transport offer:*
 - environmental modes of transport are preferable
 - public transport offer not strong enough to cover the demand for no cars in cities
- 4-*User:*
 - car drivers
- Consequences:
 - better urban planning
 - better connectivity to city centres

(Duarte & Ratti, 2018; Fournier et al., 2020; González-González et al., 2020; ITF, 2017; Medina-Tapia & Robusté, 2019)

In this study, we focus on 3 scenarios for in-depth analysis. In general, 3 scenarios are considered an ideal number not to oversimplify or complicate the assessment (Amer et al., 2013; Lloyd & Schweizer, 2014; Milakis et al., 2017). The 3 selected ones are: Replace all buses, AM in MaaS, and replace all cars. The other scenarios are important to have a holistic view of the impact of automated driving in general and might be examined in the future.

3.2. Case study Geneva

We try to answer the question “What is the potential impact of the transition from traditional transport to new mobility (AM) in European cities?” by applying the methodology on the case study of Geneva. This is even more relevant since the Covid-19 situation where shortcomings of public transport were aggravated. We start by determining the marginal costs for the minibuses. Then, the reference scenario (i.e. Geneva in 2015) is presented (the mobility behaviour and total externalities). Finally, the selected scenarios modal shifts and total externalities are determined.

3.2.1. The marginal costs for AM

This part focuses on the estimation of marginal costs for the AM. Those for the traditional modes (passenger car and the buses) are in Table 2. The latter are national values for Switzerland. For the AM, we use EU-level marginal costs due to data limitations. The values are selected from the “complete overview of country data for handbook” from van Essen et al. (2019) assessment.

Table 2: The marginal cost for buses and cars used

The category	Air pollution	Climate change	Aggregated emissions during Well-to-tank	noise	accidents	congestion
MC of cars €- <u>cent/pkm</u>	0.63	1.31	0.42	1.92	1.35	39.3
MC of bus €- <u>cent/pkm</u>	0.76	0.44	0.19	0.84	1.62	6.5

Emissions (Air pollution, climate change for the well-to-wheel)

Based on (Viere et al., 2021), the emissions of an automated electric minibus are comparable to those of an electric one. Thus, the MC for air pollution and climate changes are presumed to be similar to an electric urban minibus (van Essen et al., 2019). Therefore, the MC adopted for the AM is 0.05 €-cent/pkm, for climate change, is 0 €-cent/pkm, and for the well-to-tank is 0.54 €-cent/pkm.

Noise

The tires and the aerodynamic components cause external noise costs. The automated components do not emit significant noise. Thus, the AM is comparable to an electric vehicle in noise pollution (Jochem et al., 2016). The noise MC is predicted with Jochem et al. (2016) electric vehicles externalities, he distinguishes between night and day time MC, for our study, we use an average of 0.3 €-cent/pkm.

Accidents

According to van Essen et al. (2019), the accidents MC is estimated as a function depending on the risk of the vehicle causing an accident or being in one. The risk of being in an accident is the ratio of the number of injuries (or fatalities) and the travelled-vehicle-kilometres(Vkm). Based on the number of incidents reported from the pilot sites of AVENUE compared to the total km driven as well as (Dixit, Chand, & Nair, 2016; Filiz, 2020; Petrović, Mijailović, & Pešić, 2020)., we assume that the risk values are negligible (Viere et al., 2021). In conclusion, the MC for accidents per AV for public transport is **null**.

Congestion

Relying on the assessment from the CE Delft report and Fagnant and Kockelman (2015), we estimate that the congestion MC of AM is similar to that of an urban minibus while the automated technology leads to a reduction in the overall congestion based on its penetration rate. Table 3 shows the effect of different penetration rates of AV, on limiting overall. Similarly to (van Essen et al., 2019) simplified assumption of the marginal cost for different modes of transport, we use Shalkamy, Said, and Radwan (2015) Potential Capacity Unit⁴ for a minibus of 1.25 to estimate that, in near-capacity traffic on the majority of urban roads, the MC is 13.2 €-cent/pkm

Table 3: congestion reduction based on AV penetration rates

The penetration rate of AV.	10	50	90
Reduction of congestion	5	10	15

The summary of all costs for the minibus is in Table 4 below

Table 4: The summary of the marginal costs for automated minibuses

The category	Air pollution	Climate change	Well-to-tank aggregated emissions	noise	accidents	congestion
value in €-cent/pkm	0.05	0	0.54	0.3	0	13.2

3.2.2. The case study of Geneva - background

Geneva is the second most populated city in Switzerland, with 197 376 inhabitants. It is the capital of Geneva Canton. In order to address current and upcoming challenges in Geneva’s mobility system, in 2013, the General Planning Direction launched the ‘Mobilités 2030’, a long-term multimodal strategy for Geneva Canton (Etat de Genève, 2013). According to ‘Mobilités 2030’, we can distinguish three main challenges regarding mobility in the Canton of Geneva.

- 1- The first challenge results from the development of a mono-centric agglomeration. Currently, 75% of the jobs from the conurbation area are concentrated in Canton Geneva. As a result, public transport is underdeveloped in low-density areas.
- 2- Secondly, the city centre streets date back to the 19th century, which means they are narrow and do not absorb the current transport flow.
- 3- Thirdly, the absence of tangential routes aggravated the mobility flow. One can state that the multimodal strategy prioritises different modes of transport according to the different urban zones. This justifies the AM in MaaS scenario choice. In the centre of the conurbation and compact urban areas, the soft modes and public transport are favoured. The 2030 objectives target a shift

⁴ Passenger Car Unit (PCU) is a unit to represent the impact of a vehicle on a road expressed as the number of equivalent passenger vehicles (Pajecki et al. (2019)).

in central areas, from private vehicles and public transport to active modes of transport. This aligns with our scenarios to replace all cars and to replace all buses.

In 2012, GHG emissions from mobility were responsible for 19% of the total GHG emissions of the Canton of Geneva (Conseil d'Etat, 2017). To tackle this issue and reduce the emissions, the Climate Plan 2018-2022 for Geneva Canton comprehends as one of its axes the promotion of low-carbon mobility. Hence, the targeted integration of new mobility models within the transport ecosystem falls in line with this strategy. AM could change mobility patterns: replace motorised individual mobility, support the existing offer of public transport, and promote active modes of transport. Even more, it could make the transportation system more robust against crisis such as the Covid-19 pandemic (Jenelius & Cebecauer, 2020). The legal framework for autonomous driving has to be developed. In this regard, the Federal Office of Roads (FEDRO) has worked to adapt the traffic rules and conditions for autonomous vehicles to be integrated on the roads.

Furthermore, the 'Digital Switzerland' (OFCOM, 2018) is a strategy action plan adopted by the Federal Council in 2018 to work on the digital key factors for autonomous driving implementation. It will address data policy, the creation of data infrastructure for multimodal and interconnected traffic management, security and protection from cyber-risks.

3.3. Mobility behaviour – the reference scenario

The analysis relies on mobility behaviour data from a census (microrecensements mobilité et transports (MRMT)) realised between 2000 and 2015 by the statistical office of the Canton of Geneva (Montfort, De Faveri, & Bisso, 2019) as well as Geneva Public Transport-TPG (2016). The MRMT is an extension of a Suisse national census comprising the participation of 4500 residents. The census accounts for the evolution of mobility trends for 15 years Montfort et al. (2019). The analysis provides trip distribution and the average daily distance per modes of transport in 2015. These values help estimate the annual pkm per mode of transport. These values are computed for the city in Table 5. The population is 197,376 for the city of Geneva (Rietschin, 2015). These values are also used to estimate the new transport performance for the scenarios. The estimated transport performance is in Table 5, and the modal split for the city level are in Figure 5.

Table 5: Mobility behaviour in Geneva 2015

Mode of transport		Total transport performance million pkm =Transport performance*population	Transport performance (pkm)	average daily distance (km)	percentages of annual trips (residents)
Public mode	Bus	389.0	1,970.8	5.4	12.5
	tram metro	165.7	839.5	2.3	6.2
Private mode	Private cars	972.6	4,927.5	13.5	22.6
Active mobility	Biking	72.0	365.0	1.0	6.8
	Walking	187.3	949.0	2.6	47.6
other(including motorcycles)		72.0	365.0	1.0	4.3

Figure 5: Modal split for the Geneva 2015

Using annual transport performance from Table 5, and the marginal costs for the bus and car for Switzerland from Table 2, we estimate the total external costs for road passenger transport for Geneva in 2015. See Table 6.

Table 6: Total externalities⁵ of road transport in 2015 - Geneva in million euros

	Mode of transportation	
	private vehicles	Buses
Modal share	22.6	12.5
Externality type		
air pollution	6.1	2.9
climate change	12.7	1.7
Wtt	4.1	0.7
Noise	18.7	3.3
Accidents	13.1	6.3
Congestion	382.3	25.1
Total externalities per mode	437.0	40.0
Total externalities	477 million €	

The externalities per mode of transport (excluding congestion) are in Figure 6

⁵ Total externalities = MC × total transport performance

Figure 6: Externalities in reference scenario excluding congestion

3.4. The scenarios modal shifts and total externalities

3.4.1. Scenario 1: Replace all buses

For this scenario, we replace all the buses with the AM in the city of Geneva. The modal share of the buses in 2015 is 12.5%. (Figure 5). The estimated modal share of this scenario is compared to the reference modal share in 2015 in Figure 7

Figure 7: Modal shift for scenario -replacing all buses in Geneva

Similarly, we assume that the AM will conduct the trips of the buses with the same average distance of the bus trips from the reference scenario. This led to predicting the transport performance and consequently the total externalities in Table 7 and Figure 8 as the penetration rate for AMs is closer to 10% (table reduction congestion), the reduction rate of congestion, in this case, is considered to be 5%.

Table 7: Total externalities of road transport scenario replacing all buses - Geneva in million euros

Mode of transportation	private vehicles	buses	AM
MODAL SHARE	22.6	0.0	12.5
Externality type			
air pollution	6.1	0.0	0.2
climate change	12.7	0.0	0.0
Wtt	4.1	0.0	2.1
Noise	18.7	0.0	1.2
Accidents	13.1	0.0	0.0
Congestion	382.3	0.0	51.2
Reduced congestion due to AV penetration	363.2	0.0	48.7
Total externalities per mode	417.9	0.0	51.9
total externalities	469.8 million €		

Figure 8: Externalities in Replacing all buses scenario excluding congestion

3.4.2. Scenario 4: AM in MaaS

In this scenario, AM will replace the different share of modes of transportation. As part of a MaaS platform, they perform first and last-mile journeys. Those journeys are usually to or from a mobility hub. In this case, the mobility hub is a train station. Thus, they substitute the shares of biking, walking, and cars in intermodal journeys combined with trains. First, Gebhardt et al. (2016) work estimate that around of 17% trips are intermodal. 63% of those trips are fulfilled with a car to reach a train station, and around 10% are with a bike (Giansoldati et al., 2020). Hence, we assume that the AM replaces 10% of the car modal share (this result is also in line with preliminary data we received from the AVENUE representative survey) and around 1.7% of the bikes. Furthermore, we replace walking trips that are part of an intermodal trip to reach a train station (18.4% according to (Giansoldati et al., 2020) and that are longer than 600m (around

17% according to (Paydar et al., 2020). Hence, we assume 3% of walking trips are absorbed by the AM. Finally, the “other” modal share is also replaced by AM. See Figure 9. Plus, the AM modal share composition is in Table 8.

Figure 9: The replacement rates for AM in MaaS scenario

Table 8: Composition of the modal share of AM in the AM in MaaS scenario

AM share 19%	10	% of cars
	3	% of walking
	1.7	% of biking
	0	% of buses
	4.9	% of others

The modal shift of the AM in MaaS scenario is represented In Figure 10

Figure 10: Modal shift for scenario - AM in MaaS in Geneva

Similarly, to scenario 1 (replacing buses), the reduction rate of congestion, in this case, is considered to be 5%, and the total externalities are presented in Table 9 and Figure 11 (excluding the congestion)

Table 9: Total externalities of road transport scenario AM in MaaS - Geneva in million euros

Mode of transportation	private vehicles	buses	AM
MODAL SHARE			
Externality type	12.6	12.5	19.0
air pollution	3.4	2.9	0.3
climate change	7.1	1.7	0.0
Wtt	2.3	0.7	2.9
Noise	10.4	3.3	1.6
Accidents	7.3	6.3	0.0
Congestion	213.1	25.1	70.1
Reduced congestion due to AV penetration	202.5	23.8	66.6
Total externalities per mode	233.0	38.8	71.3
<i>total externalities</i>		337.3 million €	

Figure 11: Externalities in AM in MaaS scenario excluding congestion

3.4.3. Scenario 6: replacing all cars

We replace the car modal share in the city of Geneva (i.e. 22.6%) with the traffic circumstances of 2015 (Figure 12). The modal shift is presented in Figure 12, the total externalities are in Table 10 and those excluding the congestion are in Figure 13.

Figure 12: Modal shift for scenario - replacing all cars in Geneva

Table 10: Total externalities of road transport scenario replacing all cars in million euros

Mode of transportation	private vehicles	buses	AM
MODAL SHARE			
Externality type	0.0	12.5	22.6

air pollution	0.0	2.9	0.7
climate change	0.0	1.7	0.0
Wtt	0.0	0.7	7.5
Noise	0.0	3.3	4.1
Accidents	0.0	6.3	0.0
Congestion	0.0	25.1	182.1
Reduced congestion due to AV penetration	0.0	23.8	173.0
Total externalities per mode	0.0	38.8	185.3
total externalities		224.1	

Figure 13: Externalities in AM in MaaS scenario excluding congestion

The predicted modal shift caused by the transition from traditional modes of transport to AM in the 3 scenarios ranges between 12% and 23%. These penetration rates are consistent with previous work (i.e. (González-González et al., 2020)). They estimated the rate to be around 15% in 2030. Moreover, a great deal of attention must be paid to the estimation of the future average distance driven and the traditional mode of transport that is replaced. The MC values are significantly higher than those of other impacts. Higher penetration rates of automated technology could significantly reduce the congestion external costs (Fournier et al., 2020). Moreover, total externalities caused by cars are usually the highest. This is compliant with (ITF, 2015, 2017) scenarios on shares and automated mobility.

4. Externalities savings: results and discussion

4.1 Potential externalities savings (or costs)

The potential savings or costs incurred from replacing the traditional modes of transportation with the AM in each scenario. The costs are a comparison between the reference scenario and each of the 3 scenarios. **Error! Reference source not found.** The results are and **Error! Reference source not found.** as well as Figure 14, Figure 15, and Figure 16. Significantly, the AM introduction leads to savings in externalities of noise, accidents and climate change in the 3 cases. Moreover, the congestion externalities costs were

estimated assuming that we are replacing the traditional mode of transportation before the introduction of automated driving technology (buses and cars do not benefit from congestion reduction).

Figure 14: Externalities savings or costs caused by the modal shift (replacing all buses)

Figure 15: Externalities savings or costs caused by the modal shift (AM in MaaS)

Figure 16: Externalities savings or costs caused by the modal shift (replacing all cars)

Detailed savings and costs of externalities for each scenario are in the annex. The summary of the externalities savings/costs per category is in Table 11.

Table 11: Summary of Externalities savings or costs caused by the modal shift of the 3 scenarios

Savings/cost in million euros per scenario	Replacing all buses	AM in MaaS	Replacing all cars
air pollution	2.7	2.4	5.4
climate change	1.7	5.6	12.7
wtt	-1.4	1.1	-3.4
noise	2.1	6.7	14.5
accidents	6.3	5.8	13.1
Congestion	7	94.1	190.1
The saving/costs in million euros	-13.2€	107.8€	228.5€

Reducing congestion is a leading cause of externalities gains in our scenarios. Dominating congestion externalities are aligned with Jochem et al. (2016) and van Essen et al. (2019) results for road traffic congestion.

4.2. Discussion

Our analysis shows that scenario 6, replacing all cars with AM, has the best savings. This corroborates with most urban strategies to reduce the use of cars. Indeed, this fits with Geneva urban strategy to promote sustainable mobility (soft modes and public transport). Replacing all cars clearly leads to savings, yet it is

easier to apply in city centres and not suburban areas, this limit its gains as well as AM potential (Duarte & Ratti, 2018; ITF, 2015, 2017; McCallum, 2020). Moreover, scenario 1, replacing all buses with AM, is the worst in term of costs (and the only one with losses). It proves that AM should not compete with PT even if it is under the guise of upscaling the service, let alone replacing electric buses. Thus, we recommend that bus services not be replaced with AM. We, therefore, recommend that the bus services are not entirely replaced by AM in the city of Geneva. This also matches the simulation findings of replacing buses with shared AV in Helsinki (ITF, 2017). On a larger scale, the MaaS could reduce environmental deterioration and increase the efficiency of the shuttles even if it absorbs some active mobility means. It is the most realistic and could provide better results accompanied by TDM measures to promote active mobility. It could be part of an on-demand and door-to-door services and across the canton of Geneva to reduce the long-distance trips conducted with cars and improve connectivity to mobility hubs.

These results help orient policymakers on which strategies to adopt. Indeed, we refer to Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans SUMP as a strong guide to accompany the deployment of this technology. For instance, CoEXist, also an H2020 project has recognised 8 SUMP principles of road vehicle automation. It addresses governance structure changes, long-term implementation plans, future performance assessment, stakeholder's collaboration, citizen involvement, monitoring structures, and quality insurance. It also focuses on the axes of policy, infrastructure, planning, and traffic management (Backhaus, Rupprecht, & Franco, 2015). The results from our study support SUMP approach, targeting the reduction of the use of private cars and the integration of all modes of transport.

Moreover, another robust strategy to accompany the deployment of the AM is transport demand management TDM. Based on the results of our methodology, we suggest to replace cars in city centres and apply localised on-demand MaaS service across the Canton of Geneva. TDM pull and push measures are perfect for implementing the previously-mentioned strategy. Indeed, those measures constitute the framework of most internalisation policies of external costs (TUMI, 2018).

Moreover, other internalisation measures could help counterbalance the external costs. Policy Packaging is a way to set taxes to balance the external costs like fuel taxes and road pricing and is widely used in Europe. Another measure is the use of revenues (e.g. from policy packaging taxes) to make users accountable for the externalities they produce. The revenues will be directed towards new infrastructure or improving public transport services as long as the pricing reform is conducted to increase efficiency and equity and is public acceptable (van Essen H.P., Boon B.H., Schroten A., & Otten M., 2008). Also, Trading emissions limits greenhouse gas emissions, such as the Cap & Trade scheme, where a limit is set for emissions with tradable emission rights.

More detailed analysis is needed to better assign the proper TDM measures to deployment scenarios based on the indicator of externalities savings or costs. Also, thorough research on land-use policies could better implement the SUMP guidelines for automated technology deployment. This work will be elaborated in future work

4.3. Limitations of the model

This study provides important insights on AM as a new force capable of transforming the transportation sector. It foresees scenarios of embedding AM in societal and political contexts and their impacts. Nevertheless, these are preliminary results as on-demand issues and the integration of representative

survey to provide secured results on the expected modal share and eventual rebound effects for each city are still running. It has the potential to be more robust if the following limitations are addressed.

- i- The noise external costs depend on the population density, traffic status, and time of day. However, the data on a country level for these specific contexts is limited. This requires more finetuning to reflect the contextual impact.
- ii- Similarly, monetising congestion is complicated as it depends on an EU-level study to reach national marginal costs (Jochem et al., 2016). The meta-analysis requires inputs of speed-flow functions, demand curves, and Value-of-Time (VOT) at a large scale and poses a challenge to downscale to smaller cities.
- iii- The use of national-level marginal costs for city-level assessment is a limitation. For instance, air pollution national external costs might underestimate those on an urban level (PM emissions differ between rural and urban areas). This could be addressed using the European values for urban and rural parts in a sensitivity analysis).
- iv- We should also consider if the use of AM will increase the use of traditional forms of public transport and estimate this increase in modal share. Notably, in future assessment, we should account for Vkm increase due to induced traffic and the specification of on-demand service that requires more vehicles for a limited waiting time. It is essential to acknowledge that this technology, in case of a large scale deployment, might cause an increase in travel demand and consequently cause a rebound effect. The induced demand could be addressed using (Fagnant & Kockelman, 2018) models for shared AV and waiting times.
- v- Finally, an optimised assessment should also account for the potential demographic changes and their effect on Vkm (in Geneva rend between 2000 and 2015, shows an increase in travel demand by 10%, for example)

5. Conclusion

Automated minibuses have significant implications for the automotive ecosystem. The economic and environmental impacts of automated minibuses depend on the circumstances of their deployment. Indeed, the different scenarios show different potential impacts of deploying the automated minibuses. Under the right conditions (to support the public transport network and replace more individual motorised mobility, supportive policies, innovative technology), it could decrease the environmental footprint, reduce accidents and congestion, increase accessibility, and strengthen the public transport offer. However, under certain less favourable conditions (replacing buses and more active mobility, arbitrary policies, profit-oriented technology), they could also exacerbate current trends such as dependency on individual mobility, increased vehicle travel, and urban sprawl.

The scenarios that lead to a change in modal share from passenger cars to automated minibuses provide the most savings in the externalities, i.e. the least negative impact on the environment and the city. Fully operated automated minibuses as public transportation feeder in an intermodal city mobility concept present the most plausible and scalable scenario to benefit the city. Also, the highest savings in externalities from the implementation of the automated minibuses came from congestion for Geneva.

This study can help the city, transport operators, and policymakers become more resilient in putting in place a robust strategy to strengthen public transport and avoid future obstacles caused by events such as Covid-19 pandemics or even natural disasters exacerbated by climate change. Targeted public policies that promote sustainable forms of urban and transportation planning such as Transit-Oriented-Development and compact and mixed land use could derive more benefits from AM deployment. The assessment opens the door to developing more scenarios and considering future limitations of rebound effects and business models.

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Annex

Table 12: Externalities savings or costs caused by the modal shift (replacing all buses) in million euros

Mode of transportation	buses	minibuses	Total savings/costs per externality
air pollution	2.9	-0.2	2.7
climate change	1.7	0	1.7
Well-to-tank	0.7	-2.1	-1.4
Noise	3.3	-1.2	2.1
Accidents	6.3	0	6.3
Congestion	23.8	-51.2	-27.4
Total externalities savings/costs per modes	40.0	-51.9	
Externalities costs in million€			-13.2€

Table 13: Externalities savings or costs caused by the modal shift (AM in MaaS)

Mode of transportation	private vehicles	minibuses	Total savings/costs per externality
air pollution	2.7	-0.3	2.4
climate change	5.6	0	5.6
wtt	1.8	-2.9	-1.1
noise	8.3	-1.6	6.7
accidents	5.8	0	5.8
Congestion	160.7	-66.6	94.1
Total savings/cost per mode	204.0	-71.3	
Total externalities savings in million euros			107.8€

Table 14: Externalities savings caused by the modal shift (replacing all cars) in million euros

scenario 6

Externality type per Mode of transportation	private vehicles	minibuses	Total per category
air pollution	6.1	-0.7	5.4
climate change	12.7	0	12.7
wtt	4.1	-7.5	-3.4
noise	18.7	-4.1	14.5
accidents	13.1	0	13.1
Congestion	363.2	-173.0	190.1
Total externalities per mode	437	-185.3	
Total externalities savings in million euros	228.5€		

